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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable 9.4 reviews the initial strategy previously designed for the SPIRIT project regarding notification to National Data Protection Authorities in the light of the processing of personal data that will be conducted during the SPIRIT project.

Section 2 provides an overview about data controllers' obligation to be accountable and demonstrate compliance with data protection principles in accordance with the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and the Directive (EU) 2016/680.

In addition, Section 2.2 and Section 2.3 examine the obligation to notify data breaches by the data controllers, paying special attention to the national implementation of the Directive (EU) 2016/680 in the countries of SPIRIT LEAs end-users.

Section 3 contains a set of specific recommendations agreed with the SPIRIT Ethical Advisory Board addressing the obligations of data controllers (accountability) within the research activities.

Finally, Annex I compiles the letters of the EAB approval corresponding to the content of this Deliverable.

In the Ethical Check in M6 the Ethical Panel considered the requirements related to notification to Data Protection Authorities fulfilled. However, the Deliverable has been updated to reflect the comments and recommendations from the mid-term review. In particular, Section 4 has been added to report on, on the one hand, the status of notification to LEAs internal ethical committees/bodies to obtain approval of the SPIRIT activities before the start of the evaluation, and on the other hand, the notification of the DPO nomination to the Italian Data Protection Authority.

2 Notifications to National Data Protection Authorities

2.1 Prior consultation to Data Protection Authorities under the General Data Protection Regulation.

Due to the nature of research activities, and in particular the processing of personal data that will be conducted during the SPIRIT project, the obligation to notify Data Protection Authorities needs to be evaluated in accordance with (i) the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), (ii) the Law Enforcement Directive (LED), (iii) and the applicable national legal frameworks in which processing of personal data will take place.

The general obligation on controllers to notify or undertake prior consultation to Supervisory Authorities on the processing of personal data set out in the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC disappears under the GDPR and is replaced with the controllers' accountability obligation to demonstrate compliance with data protection principles (Article 5 (2)): "The controller shall be responsible for, and be able to demonstrate compliance with, paragraph 1 ('accountability')".

Recital 89 of the GDPR reads as follows:

"Directive 95/46/EC provided for a general obligation to notify the processing of personal data to the supervisory authorities. While that obligation produces administrative and financial burdens, it did not in all cases contribute to improving the protection of personal data. Such indiscriminate general notification obligations should therefore be abolished and replaced by effective procedures and mechanisms which focus instead on those types of processing operations which are likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons by virtue of their nature, scope, context and purposes. Such types of processing operations may be those which in, particular, involve using new technologies, or are of a new kind and where no data protection impact assessment has been carried out before by the controller, or where they become necessary in the light of the time that has elapsed since the initial processing".

In addition to the accountability requirement, Article 24 (1) of the GDPR introduces the responsibility of data controllers to demonstrate compliance with the six principles governing the processing of personal data under Article 5(1) of the GDPR (lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality). This means that data controllers should not only define data protection policies and procedures in their organisations, but also should be able to ensure and demonstrate compliance with data protection principles and provisions and how they implement such accountability requirements and instruments on an ongoing basis. Thus, they should demonstrate compliance with:

- Their internal transparent policies and processes that comply with the GDPR's requirements (for instance, establishing a data protection compliance programme);
- The implementation of the policies and processes into their organisation's activities (embedding privacy measures into internal policies and operations; implementing technical and organisational measures based on data protection and privacy by design and by default; carrying out data protection impact assessments when the processing entails potential risks for rights and freedoms of individuals; establishing security breach procedures, among others);
- The implementation of effective internal accountability measures (for instance, documenting compliance maintaining a record of data processing activities; documenting a lawful basis of each processing activity; complying with data subjects rights especially the right to information, among others);
- The implementation of internal and external controls to monitor and audit processing activities.

As explained in Section 4 of the SPIRIT First Ethical Screening Report (December 2017) no personal data will be used during the proof of concept phase of the project. Only the Valcri project research dataset¹, mock-up websites and network profiles will be used within the developing phase of the project. In order to ensure that the SPIRIT Consortium is meeting the requirement related to the accountability principle mentioned above, the following measures have been implemented at this stage of the project:

- First, due to the nature of the project and considering the research activities to be conducted within the SPIRIT project, a preliminary data protection impact assessment has been conducted before the commencement of the project².
- Second, an Authorisation for the reuse of the anonymised Valcri data sets has been signed between the West Midland Police and each partner of the SPIRIT project³
- Third, a SPIRIT Individual Data Confidentiality Agreement will be signed by those researchers involved in conducting research using Valcri data sets with the aim of ensuring that any information relating to this data will remain strictly confidential and within the confines of the research⁴.

¹ This data set was constructed by A E Solutions (AES) during the EU FP7 Project Mosaic

² The SPIRIT DPIA was provided in Section 9.2 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018)

³ See Annex 3 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018)

⁴ See Annex 4 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018)

- Fourth, a SPIRIT Data Confidentiality Agreement has been foreseen to be signed for each partner on behalf of his/her organisation before receiving Valcri Data Sets⁵. The agreement states the conditions required in order to ensure such confidentiality: i) to keep data secure by taking appropriate technical and organisational measures; ii) the Valcri data will only be used for research and not commercially; iii) the Valcri data will only be used by researchers directly involved in SPIRIT; iv) any Valcri data will be deleted at the end of the SPIRIT project.
- Fifth, the SPIRIT Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) will run periodical checks to ensure that no personal data is included within the SPIRIT dataset.
- Sixth, a SPIRIT policy has been designed for managing data re-identification risks with regards to the use of Valcri Data Set⁶.
- Seventh, a SPIRIT policy for dealing with residual risks and incidental findings has been designed and will be developed and implemented during the lifecycle of the project.⁷

2.2 Data breach notification under the GDPR

The GDPR in Article 33 (1)⁸ requires data controllers and processors to notify personal data breaches to Data Protection Authorities. This obligation does not apply if the controller of processors can demonstrate that is unlikely that the breach puts at risk the rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Moreover, Article 34 (1) requires data controllers and processors to communicate breaches to the concerned data subject, when there is a high risk that the breach results in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

The GDPR defines “personal data breach” in Article 4 (12) as “*a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed*”⁹.

⁵ See Annex 5 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018)

⁶ See Section 5.1 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018)

⁷ See SPIRIT D.9.2. Incidental Findings.

⁸ Article 33 (1) of the GDPR states: “*In the case of a personal data breach, the controller shall without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, notify the personal data breach to the supervisory authority competent in accordance with Article 55, unless the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Where the notification to the supervisory authority is not made within 72 hours, it shall be accompanied by reasons for the delay*”.

⁹ In the Opinion 03/2014⁹ on breach notification the WP29 (now EDPB) identified three types of data breaches: **confidentiality breach** (“*where there is an unauthorised or accidental disclosure of, or access to, personal data*”); **integrity breach** (“*where there is an unauthorised or accidental alteration of personal data*”); and **availability breach** (“*where there is an accidental or unauthorised loss of access to, or destruction of, personal data*”). Available here: https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp213_en.pdf

According to Recital 85 of the GDPR a data breach may adversely affect the rights and freedoms of individuals if it can result in *“loss of control over their personal data or limitation of their rights, discrimination, identity theft or fraud, financial loss, unauthorised reversal of pseudonymisation, damage to reputation, loss of confidentiality of personal data protected by professional secrecy or any other significant economic or social disadvantage to the natural person concerned”*.

Following the *Guidelines on personal data breach notification under Regulation 2016/679* published by the WP29¹⁰, data controllers shall notify data protection authorities when they have become *“aware”* that a data breach has occurred. In the opinion of WP29 a controller is *“aware”* when *“has a reasonable degree of certainty that a security incident has occurred that has led to personal data being compromised”*. WP29 pointed out that taking remedial action without delay enables data controllers to determine if personal data have been compromised or not in a data breach event. At that point, the controller must notify the data protection authority without undue delay (no later than 72 hours. If the notification is not made within 72 hours, data controllers shall justify the reasons for the delay).

WP29 also provides a set of factors to be considered in order to assess the risk to individuals as a result of a breach. In particular: the type of breach; the nature, sensitivity, and volume of personal data; ease of identification of individuals; severity of consequences for individuals; special characteristics of the individual; special characteristics of the data controller; the number of affected individuals¹¹.

The information to be provided to the supervisory authority (Article 33 (3)) is:

- The nature of the personal data breach (including where possible, number of data subjects concerned; categories and number of personal data records concerned)
- Name and contact details of the Data Protection Officer or the contact point that can provide more detailed information on data breach incident
- Consequences of the personal data breach
- Measures taken by the controller to address the personal data breach in order to mitigate the potential adverse effects for the data subjects concerned.

Article 34 (1) assesses when personal data needs to be communicated to the data subject. In this regard, individuals should be informed when there is a high risk to their rights and freedoms as a result of a data breach. This communication of a breach to individuals should be made as well

¹⁰ Available here: http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=612052

¹¹ WP29 suggests the use of the methodology of assessing the severity of a breach produced by the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) to data controllers and processors for designing their breach management response plan. ENISA, Recommendations for a methodology of the assessment of severity of personal data breaches is available at: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/dbn-severity>

without delay according to Recital 86 of the GDPR. The information to be provided when notifying individuals is:

- A description of the nature of the breach
- Name and contact details of the Data Protection Officer or the contact point
- A description of the consequences of the breach
- A description of the detailed measures taken/proposed by the controller to address the breach in order to mitigate its possible adverse consequences for the data subject.

An internal breach reporting procedure has been designed within the SPIRIT project to react promptly, efficiently and effectively whenever a data breach occurs during the proof of concept phase of the project. Therefore, when a member of the Consortium detects a data breach this will be communicated immediately to the Ethical Lead Partner of the project (UAB-IDT). They will contact the SPIRIT Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the EAB with the aim of: i) providing a quick assessment and guide to address the personal data breach and mitigate the potential adverse impacts for the data subjects concerned taking into account the typology of the data breach; ii) and, making a decision on the remedial actions to take to correct/minimise/inform the concerned supervisory authority and the data subject in accordance with Article 33 (3) and Article 34 of the GDPR.

2.3 Prior consultation to Data Protection Authorities under the Law Enforcement Directive.

The Law Enforcement Directive in its Article 28 (1) establishes the conditions under which a prior consultation to the supervisory authority is required by the Law Enforcement Agencies:

- when *“a data protection impact assessment as provided for in Article 27 indicates that the processing would result in a high risk in the absence of measures taken by the controller to mitigate the risk”*
- or when *“the type of processing, in particular, where using new technologies, mechanisms or procedures, involves a high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects”*.

In addition, the Supervisory Authorities’ obligation to provide a list of processing operations subject to prior consultation before starting the processing activities is set out in paragraph (3); in paragraph (4) and according to Article 27 of the Directive it is contained the controllers’ obligation to provide a Data Protection Impact Assessment to the Supervisory Authority and any other information requested with regard to the processing activities. The aim of providing such information is to enable the Supervisory Authority to assess compliance, focusing on the potential

risks for the data subject involved and on the related safeguards. Finally, the decision-making process of the Supervisory Authority is laid down in paragraph 5 of the said article.

Notwithstanding the foregoing, the SPIRIT Consortium is aware that Directive 2016/680 has not been transposed at this stage of the project in all Member States of the EU. To that end, it has reviewed the status of the implementation of the Directive in LEA's countries where the evaluation and trials will take place:

Belgium

- The Law of 30 July 2018 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data ('The Belgian DPL')¹² implemented the GDPR and transposed the Law Enforcement Directive.
- Relevant provisions of the Belgian DPL concerning the aim of this Deliverable:
 - **Article 29 (5)** sets out the obligation of the data controller of carrying out processing activities not only in strict compliance with the data protection principles but also demonstrating that complies with them (accountability principle).
 - **Article 55** establishes data controllers' obligations in relation with processing activities
 - **Article 58** declares the need to carry out a Data Protection Impact Assessment when the processing would entail a high risk for the rights and freedoms of individuals if the controller does not take proper measures to mitigate the risk previous the starting of the processing activities
 - **Article 59 (1)** states the conditions under which it is mandatory to consult the competent supervisory authority of the controller prior to the processing of personal data. Particularly, it will be necessary if a DPIA points out that the processing would represent a high risk if the controller does not take measures to minimise the impact of such processing on rights and freedoms of individuals; or if the use of new technologies, procedures or mechanisms the processing would entail a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals. The competent supervisory authority may provide a list of processing operations to be subject to prior consultation in accordance with paragraph (1). Information to be provided to the supervisory authority is listed in paragraph (3), mainly a DPIA and any other information requested by the Supervisory Authority that considers necessary to perform its assessment on the risk derived from the processing activities to the rights and

¹² Law of 30 July 2018 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data was published on 5 September 2018 in the Belgian Official Gazette. The Law is available in French and in Dutch: https://www.gegevensbeschermingsautoriteit.be/sites/privacycommission/files/documents/Wet_Loi_30_07_2018.pdf

freedoms of individuals. In six weeks (from the receipt of the request consultation) the Belgian Data Protection Authority (BDPA) shall provide in writing a non-binding notice to the controller/and to the processor (if applicable) informing of its opinion concerning the processing and the measures implemented to minimise the impact on individuals' rights and freedoms. If the BDPA applies an extension (1 month) in order to provides its opinion, this circumstance needs to be communicated to the controller justifying the delay.

- **Article 61** provides the procedure concerning data breach notifications to the supervisory authority. This provision follows basically the procedures and conditions established within the GDPR in relation with the notification of a data breach to the supervisory authorities. The requirement is the same, only if the data breach entails high risks to the rights and freedoms of a data subject, then it is mandatory to communicate the data breach to BDPA¹³.

United Kingdom

- The Data Protection Act 2018¹⁴ (DPA) implemented both the GDPR and the Law Enforcement Directive and establishes data protection obligations on the processing of personal data for national security purposes.
- Relevant provisions of Part 3 of the DPA related to the Law Enforcement processing considering the aim of this Deliverable:
 - **Part 3 Chapter 2**¹⁵ of the DPA establishes the accountability principle which entails the requirement of demonstrating compliance with the data protection principles as defined in this Part 3 of the Act.
 - **Section 65 (2)** of Chapter 4 states the conditions under which a prior consultation to the Commissioner (ICO) is required to be performed by LEAs acting as data controllers. Thus, *“the controller must consult the Commissioner prior to the processing if a data protection impact assessment prepared under section 64 indicates that the processing of the data would result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals (in the absence of measures to mitigate the risk)”*. Subsection (3) provides the necessary information to be provided to the Commissioner (basically, the DPIA in which such high risk has been identified or additional information previously requested by the Commissioner). If the Commissioner considers that the processing would be unlawful then the Commissioner

¹³ The Belgian Data Protection Authority provides information related to the procedures and forms to notify a data breach. This information is available at: <https://www.dataprotectionauthority.be/data-breach-notification-form>

¹⁴ Data Protection Act 2018 : http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/pdfs/ukpga_20180012_en.pdf

¹⁵ See: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/part/3/chapter/2/enacted>

must provide a written advice (no later than 6 weeks beginning with the receipt of the request for consultation) to the controller or the processor (if the controller is using a data processor). If the Commissioner takes longer than 6 weeks, then a justification should be provided.

- **Section 66 (1)** of Chapter 4 establishes the need to implement technical and organisational security measures for processing in accordance with the risks identified. Subsection (2)¹⁶ provides specific security measures when automated processing is carry out by LEAs.
- **Section 67¹⁷** of Chapter 4 related to the notification of a personal data breach to the Commissioner. This provision follows basically the procedures and conditions established within the GDPR in relation with the notification of a data breach to the supervisory authorities. The requirement is the same, only if the data breach entails high risks to the rights and freedoms of a data subject, then it is mandatory to communicate the data breach to the Commissioner. The Commissioner provides procedures and forms to notify a data breach in its official website¹⁸.
- **Section 68¹⁹** of Chapter 4 covers the communication of a data breach to a data subject.
- **Section 69²⁰** of Chapter 4 related to the obligation of designing a Data Protection Officer

Poland

No transposed yet.

Greece

No transposed yet

Non-EU LEA

In relation with the **non-EU LEA** participating in the project, SERBLEA (Serbia), it should be noted that the activities foreseen in Serbian territory will be conducted in strict compliance with the ethical and legal rules and guidelines set up within the SPIRIT project, including the opinions, guidelines and recommendations of the EAB. Moreover, SERBLEA has signed a Service Contract with the SPIRIT Consortium represented by LUTECH S.P.A (“SPIRIT Technical Partners”) agreeing to conduct the SPIRIT research activities in terms of personal data in full compliance with the GDPR,

¹⁶ See: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/section/66/enacted>

¹⁷ See: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/section/67/enacted>

¹⁸ ICO procedures and forms to report a data breach: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/report-a-breach/#>

¹⁹ See: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/section/68/enacted>

²⁰ See: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/section/69/enacted>

the Law Enforcement Directive, their national and local provisions, the SPIRIT DPO and the EAB decisions and recommendations²¹.

Nevertheless, when SPIRIT ethical and legal rules and guidelines refer to national legislation for a specific matter the EAB and the SPIRIT DPO will check, prior to the development of the activities that the applicable rules are compatible with the legislation of at least one Member State. Finally, feedback from the training and evaluation processes will be given back to the SPIRIT Consortium after full anonymization. The EAB will be in charge of monitoring that no personal data from SERBLEA databases are transferred to the SPIRIT project.

2.4 Data breach notification under the Law Enforcement Directive

Article 30 of the Directive establishes the conditions under which a data breach should be notified to the national supervisory authority. It should be noticed that the regime of data breach notification under this legal instrument does not differ from the procedures established by the GDPR on this subject. However, the communication to the data subject is not required if any of the following conditions met according to Article 31 (3):

(a) the controller has implemented appropriate technological and organisational protection measures, and those measures were applied to the personal data affected by the personal data breach, in particular those that render the personal data unintelligible to any person who is not authorised to access it, such as encryption;

(b) the controller has taken subsequent measures which ensure that the high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects referred to in paragraph 1 is no longer likely to materialise;

(c) it would involve a disproportionate effort. In such a case, there shall instead be a public communication or a similar measure whereby the data subjects are informed in an equally effective manner.

In addition, Recital 15 of the Directive points out that Member States should not be precluded from providing higher safeguards than those established in the Directive for the protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subject with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities. As mentioned above all relevant data protection supervisory authorities for the SPIRIT project have their own mechanism to notify a data breach. Table 1 provides the links to the national

²¹ See the Service Contract signed by SERBLEA in Annex 1, Section 6 of the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (April 2018). The Service Contract also provides contract conditions related to the access of personnel from SPIRIT technical partners to LEAs facilities (Section B) and with regard to the license for the SPIRIT prototype during and after the project ends (Section C)

supervisory authorities and their correspondent procedures and forms to notify a data breach with regard to the LEAs participating in the project:

Table 1: Data Protection Supervisory Authorities and procedures/forms for notifying a data breach in each SPIRIT end-user’s country

LEA Country	end-user	Data Protection Authority	Procedures/Forms for notifying a data breach
Belgium		Belgium Data Protection Authority (BDPA): https://www.dataprotectionauthority.be	https://www.dataprotectionauthority.be/data-breach-notification-form
United Kingdom		Information Commissioner’s Office (ICO): https://ico.org.uk	https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/report-a-breach/
Poland		Office for Personal Data Protection (UODO): https://uodo.gov.pl/en	https://uodo.gov.pl/en/573/935
Greece		Hellenic Data Protection Authority (HDP): http://www.dpa.gr/portal/page?_pageid=33,40911&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL	http://www.dpa.gr/portal/page?_pageid=33,215235&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL
Serbia		Commissioner for Information of Public Importance and Protection of Personal Data: https://www.poverenik.rs/en/	

2.5 The obligation to notify in the Data Protection doctrine

The obligation to notify has been examined by legal and ethical scholars, as it is deemed essential to preserve the recipient’s rights. The GDPR waives some obligations to companies, if they can prove the safety and security of data processing. The rapporteur of the European Parliament for the EU's General Data Protection Regulation, J.P. Albrecht, has laid some clear explanations about it:

The replacement of prior notifications to DPAs by a strict application of the accountability principle is reducing unnecessary red tape for companies. The introduction of several provisions for more transparency and simple information policies is paramount in order to give back control to consumers and make their consent meaningful again. New innovative concepts like the right to data portability, standardised privacy icons and data protection by design and default are opening wide opportunities to foster innovation and competition in the direction of data protection and consumer friendly products and services. The risk-based approach applied in important provisions like breach notifications, data protection impact assessments or the appointment of data protection officers brings a reasonable approach for businesses but also effective protection of the fundamental right to data protection in the digital ecosphere of tomorrow. (Albrecht, 2016: 288)

Scholars have debated extensively some crucial issues of the GDPR: (i) in order to satisfy the accountability requirement, this increases the need for transparency²², (ii) “a meaningful right to explanation is not legally mandated by the GDPR”²³, (iii) “too much is expected from controllers, for whom compliance is too complex even if they want to follow the law”²⁴, (iv) “transparency-enhancing techniques cannot be realised by technological tools alone, but need to be intertwined with processes that provide the necessary information”²⁵.

In light of this debate, the SPIRIT approach endorses a cautionary principle, (i) differentiating research obligations from LEA’s investigations, (ii) considering the necessary evolving nature of the DPIA originally performed, according to the different stages of the project, (iii) adopting a systemic and holistic approach, in which recommendations can take into account the whole lifecycle of the data being processed, the nature and degree of the possible risks of personal data breaches, and the protections already set to anticipate and eventually face them. We consider this approach to be

²² “In the future, more transparency will be required of companies. In order to satisfy the accountability requirement and to provide information to data subjects, data processing will also have to be documented in a more comprehensive manner than has hitherto been the case. The heightened requirements governing information require, in their turn, adaptations of data protection notices, cookie notices, consent forms, works agreements etc. Moreover, the mechanisms inherent in the advance risk audit will have to be adapted to the requirements governing the data protection impact assessment. Standard settings will also have to be reviewed and data processing for purposes other than those for which data was initially processed will have to be investigated for compatibility”. (Freiherr and Zeiter, 2014: 581)

²³ “Despite the claims in contrary, given the proliferation of automated decision-making and automated processing of data to support human decision-making (ie ‘not solely’), this is a critical gap in transparency and accountability. The GDPR appears to give strong protection against automated decision making but, as it stands, the protections may prove ineffectual. [...]. A right to explanation of specific decisions is not legally mandated by the safeguards contained in Article 22(3), or notification duties in Articles 13 and 14. As proven by the 1995 Directive, the right of access is ambiguous. However, the GDPR’s right of access provides a right to explanation of system functionality, what we call a ‘right to be informed’, restricted by the interests of data controllers and future interpretations of Article 15. (Wachter, Mittelstadt and Floridi, 2017: 21).

²⁴ “While an important objective of the data protection reform is ‘simplifying the regulatory environment, thus eliminating unnecessary costs and reducing the administrative burden’, the reduction of some administrative burdens (such as notification) is amply compensated by the creation of new ones. Article 22 requires the controller to adopt policies and to ‘be able to demonstrate that the processing of personal data is performed in compliance with this Regulation’. [...] Hence, the complexity of data protection law, which is increasing instead of decreasing, together with more ex ante and ex post paperwork and checklist obligations, create a situation in which controllers will, at best, blindly follow a set of rules to be rule-compliant, while (still) not understanding much about data protection. The fallacy of creating more rules to ensure controller compliance will not lead to data protection law being a dead letter, as the letters are (at best) obediently followed, but it will result in the law being a zombie: it seems to live but lacks a vital spirit.” (Koops, 2014: 8)

²⁵ “Transparency-enhancing techniques cannot be realised by technological tools alone but need to be intertwined with processes that provide the necessary information. Also, support of transparency for users has to be ensured no matter if the user employs specific technological solutions or not. In the following, the necessary processes for achieving transparency and complying with all of the notification obligations (of users or other data subjects as well as supervisory authorities) will not be further discussed, but they have to be considered in each specific case of privacy by design.” (Danezis et al. 2015: 45).

compatible with the concerns expressed by the critical evaluation of GDPR and the Directive and coping with the situation.

3 Recommendations on Notifications to National Data Protection Authorities for the SPIRIT Project

According to the Data Protection Impact Assessment²⁶ carried out by the Ethical Lead Partner of the SPIRIT project, UAB-IDT, the processing of personal data within the SPIRIT Project will take place only during the evaluation phase of the SPIRIT platform and the training of LEA investigators in its use. Personal data to be used in the SPIRIT project will have two different origins: LEAs end-users databases and Open Source Data.

Articles 5.1 letter b) of the General Data Protection Regulation and 4.1 letter b) of Directive 2016/680 establish that one of the conditions for the processing of personal data is that data is

“collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and no further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes”.

Within the SPIRIT project the purpose principle needs to be evaluated in relation with two types of data: i) personal data contained in the partners LEAs databases; ii) and open source data publicly available on the web.

LEAs Databases

Personal data contained in LEAs databases has been previously collected for the purpose of fighting crime, allowing LEAs analysts and agents to perform their duties of identifying potential criminal activities and individuals or organisations responsible for them. The aim is gathering evidence to be used in a court of law for prosecution and conviction. Therefore, the collection of these data fall under the scope of Directive 2016/680 which defines on Article 1 its subject-matter as

“...the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security”

However, within the SPIRIT project, LEAs will use personal data contained in their own databases for a different purpose, that is, for evaluating the SPIRIT platform and training their personnel. This implies the re-use of personal data contained in LEAs databases for a purpose different of that for which the data was originally collected. It also entails the risks of other partners from the SPIRIT Consortium having access to this personal data. Article 4.2 of Directive 2016/680 provides legal grounds justifying the re-use of LEAs databases within the SPIRIT project and sets out the potential risks associated:

²⁶ SPIRIT Data Protection Impact Assessment was presented to the EC twice. Firstly, within the Addendum to the SPIRIT First Ethical Screening Report (5th December 2017, Section 5) and secondly, within the SPIRIT Reply to the Ethics Second Assessment Report (31th April 2018, Section 9).

“Providing by the same or another controller for any of the purposes set out in Article 1(1) other than that for which the personal data are collected shall be permitted in so far as: a) the controller is authorised to process such personal data for such a purpose in accordance with Union or Member State law; and b) processing is necessary and proportionate to that other purpose in accordance with Union or Member State law”

Moreover, article 4.3 of the Directive includes the lawful processing of such data for scientific purposes particularly when they are related to the purposes of *“the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, including the safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security”*. The use of personal data in SPIRIT activities is covered by Article 4 (2) and 4 (3) of the Directive since it can be considered a scientific use for the purposes of Article 1 (1). In fact, the aim of the SPIRIT project is to develop a semantically rich sense-making capability to facilitate LEA investigators in the resolution of different facets of criminal and terrorists’ identity. This will, in the short term, improve collaboration between investigators and reduce investigation time, which will lead to crimes being solved more rapidly. In the medium term, LEA personnel will be provided with better tools to assist their very specialised daily work, which will lead to a better identification and understanding of criminal activities. In the longer term the quicker solving of crimes will reduce the costs of investigations and thus improve the relationships of victims and their families with LEAs, by reducing the impact of the crimes on their daily lives. New and wide-ranging crime prevention techniques will be discovered thereby reducing the activities of organised crime and terrorists’ groups.

Due to the fact that the Directive 2016/680 is not yet implemented in some national legislations of the SPIRIT LEAs end-users as mentioned in Section 2.2 and considering that national rules may be more restrictive of the use of personal data contained in LEA databases, the SPIRIT lead partner jointly with the EAB provide a set of recommendations at this stage of the project (without prejudice to readdress the notification issue when the transposition of the Directive occurs in those SPIRIT end-users partners that have not yet implemented this legal instrument in their national legal frameworks):

1. The minimum standard for the protection of fundamental rights in relation to the re-use of personal data from LEA databases within the SPIRIT project will be the one defined in the ethical guidelines and legal requirements contained in the General Data Protection Regulation and Directive 2016/680 as interpreted by the SPIRIT Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) and the Spirit Data Protection Officer (SPIRIT DPO) within the context of the SPIRIT project.

In that sense, the EAB and the SPIRIT Data Protection Officer will request from the director of each LEAs end-users partner a declaration of compliance with the applicable national and EU legislation with the aim of ensuring that all data processing is carried out within their organisations in accordance with the applicable legal framework mentioned above, particularly in full compliance with the accountability requirement. A data protection policy

of their organisations will be also provided jointly with the declaration of compliance. The EAB and the SPIRIT DPO will evaluate such data protection policies that will be received at M4 of the project and if considered necessary they will evaluate the possibility to notify the supervisory data protection authorities with regards those EU countries that not provide a sufficient data protection policy according to the EU legislation.

It is important to stress at this point that other measures have been taken by the SPIRIT Consortium to ensure data processing compliance within the EU and national legislation on data protection as for instance the signature of a Service Contract between the technical partners of the Consortium and the LEAs end-users. This contract in Section A states that the collaboration between these partners in terms of protection of personal data will be conducted in strict compliance with the ethical and legal requirements contained in the legal instruments mentioned above as well as the EAB and the SPIRIT DPO decisions and recommendations.

2. More restrictive rules may apply when imposed by: (i) the different national and/or local ethical and legal frameworks; (ii) and the authorities of the country of each LEA in the SPIRIT project. In that case, the EAB and the SPIRIT DPO previous consultation of the LEAs end-user partners will readdress any issue that needs to be balanced as a consequence of regulatory differences between the EU applicable legislation and the national or local legal frameworks.
3. Although the re-use is covered by the purpose principle, in order to ensure compliance with the data minimisation and proportionality principles, when allowed by the national framework, access to personal data from LEA databases may be granted to other members of the SPIRIT Consortium on a need-to-know basis and only after specific authorisation by the relevant authorities and/or the EAB and SPIRIT DPO.
4. Feedback from the training and evaluation processes will be given back to the SPIRIT Consortium after full anonymization. The EAB and SPIRIT DPO will review that no personal data is transferred from LEA's databases to the SPIRIT project.
5. In any case, the relevant authorisation for the re-use of data shall be provided by the controller of the data to the SPIRIT Consortium at least two months before the start of the training and evaluation activities and shall be reviewed by the EAB and SPIRIT DPO.

Open Source Data publicly available

During the training and evaluation activities LEA investigators will collect, through the SPIRIT platform, open source data publicly available, including personal data. The fact that this data is available does not preclude however the need to fulfil the purpose and lawfulness principles. The open source data will be collected, within SPIRIT, for a double purpose, first, LEAs will use the data collected in their day-today work and therefore in real investigation. From this perspective, the

purpose principle is respected, as per article 1.1 of Directive 2016/580, since data will be collected for the investigation and detection of criminal offences.

However, LEAs will also collect data as a means to test the SPIRIT platform and train their personnel in the use of the new technology, adding a second purpose to the collection. This second purpose can be considered covered by articles 4.2 and 4.3 of the Directive but also by article 9 that sets specific processing conditions and in particular creates two exceptions to the general purposes regulated in article 1.1.: (i) cases where Union and/or Member States law authorised the processing for this other purpose and (ii) purposes related to tasks that have been assigned to the LEAs by Member State law.

As was the case with the LEA databases, the Consortium is aware that Directive 2016/680 is not yet transposed in some national legal frameworks of the SPIRIT LEAs end-users. Therefore, some rules have already been granted at this stage:

1. The minimum standard for the protection of fundamental rights in relation to the collection of publicly available personal data from open source within the SPIRIT project will be the one defined in the ethical guidelines and legal requirements contained in the General Data Protection Regulation and Directive 2016/680 as interpreted through the opinions and recommendations of the EAB and the Spirit DPO.
2. More restrictive rules may apply when imposed by the different national and or local ethical and legal frameworks and authorities of the country of each partner LEA. As explained with regard to the use of LEAs databases the EAB and the SPIRIT DPO previous consultation of the LEAs end-user partners will readdress any issue related to open source data that needs to be balanced as a consequence of regulatory differences between the EU applicable legislation and the national or local legal frameworks

As explained in Section 2.3 of this Deliverable the participation of SERBIA (Non-EU country LEA) within the project is subject to the following rules:

1. The activities foreseen in Serbian territory will be conducted in strict compliance with the ethical and legal rules and guidelines set up within the SPIRIT project, the Service Contract signed with the technical partners agreeing the terms and conditions under which the protection of personal data (among others) will be conducted and specially those opinions and recommendations of the EAB.
2. Whenever SPIRIT ethical and legal rules and guidelines refer to national legislation for a specific matter the EAB and the SPIRIT DPO will check, prior to the development of the activities, that the applicable national rules are compatible with the legislation of at least one EU Member State.

3. Feedback from the training and evaluation processes will be given back to the SPIRIT Consortium after full anonymization.

4 Update on the notification to the LEAs ethical committees and the Italian DPO

Several steps have been taken in order to notify relevant and competent authorities and bodies, following the requirements from the Ethical check in M6 and from the applicable Data Protection legislation. In particular:

1. **LEAS Ethical Commitees:** UAB-IDT started a procedure to notify LEAs internal ethical bodies, as foreseen in D9.3. The first step is the communication from the LEAs of the contact details of such bodies as well as the procedure that needs to be followed. The procedure varies in each country and in each LEA. The UAB-IDT is working with each one of the LEA partners to personalize the notification and to respond to the requests addressed to each body. However, and as a minimum content of the information provided to the LEA ethical bodies, Annex VII of Deliverable 9.3, shows the letter signed by the Coordinator LUTECH and the list of documents that the information package contains. LEAs Internal Ethics Committees will be notified on the 1st of September 2019, provided that all LEA partners have provided information and contact details of their institutions, as requested by the Ethical-lead partner and reminded by the EAB. A reminder will be send on the 1st of December 2020 to those Committees that have not still produced an opinion or recommendation.
2. **Technical/academic Ethical Commitees:** The UAB-IDT, together with technical partners, has identified competent ethical commitees and has started a process to obtain approvals or positives opinions from them. For Germany, the recently appointed Fraunhofer Ethics Committee for Security-Relevant Research (REC) (<https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/about-fraunhofer/corporate-responsibility/research-and-development/ethics-committee-for-security-relevant-research.html>) has been identified as relevant for the SPIRIT research. The Ethical-lead partner, in collaboration with the FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V. will start the procedure for an opinion/approval on the 1st of September 2019.

For Sweden, the recently appointed Swedish Ethical Review Authority (<https://etikprovningmyndigheten.se>) has been identified as relevant for the SPIRIT research. The Ethical-lead partner, in collaboration with the University of Linköping, will start the procedure for an opinion/approval on the 1st of September 2019.

For Italy, no competent ethical committee has been identified yet. The Ethical-lead partner, in collaboration with Lutech, Live/Synthema and CEPIC, are still working on finding a relevant one.

For Spain two positive opinions have been obtained, one from the UAB Ethical Committee and one from the Catalan Association of Artificial Intelligence. The opinions can be found annexed to Deliverable 9.3.

- 3. Italian National Data Protection Authority:** Article 37.7 of the GDPR requires the Controller to notify the National Data Protection Authority of the appointment of a DPO and to provide the contact details. The Italian Data Protection Authority has made available an online procedure to communicate such appointments that can be found here:
<https://servizi.gdpd.it/comunicazionerpd/s/compilazione-comunicazione>

Lutech has started the communication process for the appointment of Mr. Massimiliano Bellavista as SPIRIT DPO.

5. References

- Albrecht, J.P., 2016. "Foreword. How the GDPR will change the world". *Eur. Data Prot. L. Rev.*, 2: 287-289.
- Article 69 Working Party. Guidelines on Personal data breach notification under Regulation 2016/679 (wp250rev.01).
- Danezis, G., Domingo-Ferrer, J., Hansen, M., Hoepman, J.H., Metayer, D.L., Tirtea, R. and Schiffner, S., 2015. "Privacy and Data Protection by Design-from policy to engineering". *arXiv preprint arXiv:1501.03726*.
- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 89)
- Freiherr, A.V.D.B. and Zeiter, A., 2016. „Implementing the EU General Data Protection Regulation: A Business Perspective". *Eur. Data Prot. L. Rev.*, 2: 576-581.
- Karyda, M., & Mitrou, L. 2016. "Data Breach Notification: Issues and Challenges for Security Management". MCIS. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Data-Breach-Notification%3A-Issues-and-Challenges-for-Karyda-Mitrou/0b274586fc727c22f19d7a448-4cb365ea20f4123>
- Koops, B.J. 2014. "The trouble with European data protection law". *International Data Privacy Law*, 4 (4): 250-261. doi: 10.1093/idpl/ipu023.
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1)
- Wachter, S., Mittelstadt, B. and Floridi, L., 2017. "Why a right to explanation of automated decision-making does not exist in the general data protection regulation". *International Data Privacy Law*, 7 (2): 76-99.

ANNEX I – EAB Deliverable approval

Monday 29th October 2018

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

Dear Sir/Madam

EUROPEAN UNION SPIRIT PROJECT

I hereby declare that I have read, and I accept the outcomes of the deliverables foreseen for M3 carried out in the European Union SPIRIT Project, including docs D9.1 on the Informed Consent, D9.2 on the Incidental Findings, D9.3 on the Ethics Advisory Board and D9.4 on Notification to National Data Protection Authorities.

The Project has successfully completed this round of deliverables in strict accordance with rules and principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2018/679 (GDPR) and Directive (EU) 2016/680.

Please let me know if I can be of further assistance.

Yours sincerely,

Ugo Pagallo
Professor of Jurisprudence at the Department of Law,
University of Turin,
Turin, Italy

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Yours sincerely,

Lilian Mitrou
Professor at Department of Information and
Communication System Engineering,
University of the Aegean, Greece

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Yours sincerely,

Virginia Dignum
Full Professor at Department of Computing Science,
Umeå universitet, Sweden

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Yours sincerely,

David Watts
Professor of Information Law and Policy
La Trobe Law School,
La Trobe University, Australia

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Please let me know if I can be of further assistance.

Yours sincerely,

Giovanni Sartor
Full Professor in Legal Informatics-Computers and Law
at University of Bologna,
Bologna, Italy